

IMPACT OF MISSION STATEMENT DEVELOPMENT ON NON-OIL EXPORT PERFORMANCE IN WOMEN'S ORGANIZATIONS IN INTERNATIONAL TRADE IN ABUJA, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study examines mission statement development and performance of non-oil export: a study of women organization in international trade in Abuja – Nigeria. The study used survey research design and data were collected from the respondents who form the sample size of the study. The population of this study is one thousand five hundred which are members in Nigeria. The Sample size determined using a formula developed by Gill, Johnson and Clark in 2010 which was recorded the as three hundred and six (306). The study used Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) to analyzed the data with the Smart Pls. The study found that firm's mission statement development significantly affects competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality in non-oil export with a particular reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria. This implies that mission statement development contributes significantly to the performance in terms of competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality in non-oil export with a particular reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria. The study recommended that mission statement development in terms of periodic reviews and updates of the mission statement that reflect environmental changes, purpose, values, and target customers, as well as sufficient resources to carry out the mission. All of these contribute significantly to a firm's competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality. Efforts should be made by the leadership of the Organization of Women in International Trade to regularly update their mission statement that reflects environmental changes, purpose, values, and target customers, allocate adequate resources to carry out the mission statement to foster the firm's competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, service quality

Keywords Mission Statement Development, Performance, service quality, market share

Introduction

1.0 Background to the study

Without a clear objective, a company cannot track its progress, evaluate its performance, or chart its existence in relation to its competitors. A company with a mission is like a journey without a destination. The organization's

mission statement establishes the values, principles, and rules that will be used to manage the business and assure greater performance in terms of profitability, market share, and other metrics, as well as relations with stakeholders. Mission gives tasks soul and meaning as well as inspires, motivates, and grow teamwork to carry out supportive actions to achieve superior performance in the organization. The mission will then serve as a point of agreement to steer and guide decision-making at every level of management to ensure effective performance. A vital component of an organization's strategic planning is its mission statement.

A mission statement describing the organization's goals and direction have been developed over time by a women's organization in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria. The organization is inspired to make progress in the future in order to improve performance in terms of perceived customer satisfaction, market share, competitiveness, and service quality. However, non-oil export performance with regard to women's organizations in global trade in Abuja, Nigeria, is not improving (Pilot study, 2022). The variables (goal statement and performance) were explored using various organizations and industries in various locations, such as Nigeria and Kenya, in previous research by Bonn, Caren, and Zachary (2018), Sajjad, Sajjad, and Mohammad (2020), and Oluwaseyi, Onu, and Akinlabi (2021). None of these studies, however, combined measures of performance for perceived customer happiness, market share, competitiveness, and service quality. Additionally, none of this research employed the Partial Least Method to analyze the data or referenced women's organizations engaged in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria, when examining the variables.

Examining the impact of mission statements on non-oil export performance with reference to women's organizations engaged in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria, is the goal of this study. The specific goals are to assess the impact of the mission statement on perceived customer satisfaction of non-oil export with reference to women organizations in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria, the competitiveness of non-oil export with reference to women organizations in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria, and the market share of non-oil export with reference to women organizations in international trade in Abuja, Nigeria. The study measured performance with market share, competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, and service quality.

The hypotheses are stated in a null form as follows:

H01: mission statement has no significant effect on competitiveness of non-oil export with reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria

H02: mission statement has no significant effect on the market share of non-oil export with reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria

H03: mission statement has no significant effect on perceived customer satisfaction of non-oil export with reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria

H04: mission statement has no significant effect on service quality of non-oil export with reference to women organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria

2.0 Concept of Mission Statement

Mission statement defines the scope of company's operations and distinguishes the company from similar ones (David, 2015). Mission statements are widely believed to be antecedents to any strategy effort (Thompson &

Strickland 1992; Wheelen & Hunger, 1998; Lyles et al. 1993 cited by David, 2015). More fundamentally, mission statements are supposed to capture the overriding purpose of an organization in line with the values and expectations of stakeholders and should typically answer the questions: „what business are we in? (Johnson et al., 2018); and „what is our business for? (Drucker, 1973 cited in David, 2015). Also, mission statements are said to do a good job in capturing corporate level strategy in terms of scope, boundaries and value creation (Johnson, 2018). Achua and Lussier (2016) defines organization mission statement as an enduring statement of purpose that distinguishes one organization from the other similar enterprises. Ireland et al., (2016) asserts that a good mission statement should focus on the needs that the organization’s products/services are meeting.

Kantabutra and Avery (2015) argue that vision on the other hand is an ambitious view of the future that everyone within the organization can believe in and that is not readily attainable yet offers a better future than what now exists. Leonard and Huang, (2015) assert that a well-defined mission statement can unify and energize internal stakeholders while enhancing external stakeholders’ perceptions, expectations, and possible actions. A Mission statement is a clear definition of the organization’s business. It involves stating the business’s overall strategy, and may include what strengths the company has, what areas it wants to be in, who it is, and what it is trying to do (Alkhafaji, 2015). Ganu (2015) defines organization’s mission as a set of values, beliefs and norms of behavior shared by its (a firm’s) members that influence employees’ preferences and behavior. Henry (2018) and Papulova (2015) defined a mission statement as a way in which the organization communicates the business it is to the outside world. Mission statements communicate the strategic direction of the organization to stakeholders in order to guide strategy formulation (Ekpe, Eneh, & Inyang, 2015). The mission statement shows a sense of shared expectation amongst employees and communicates a public image of the organization to important stakeholders (Analoui & Karami, 2002) cited by (Eze, Akyüz & Opusunju, 2020).

2.1 Concept of Performance

Performance is defined as a reflection of how the institution uses financial and human resources and uses them efficiently and effectively in a way that makes it able to analyze its goals (Mahdi & Belkacem, 2017). The performance is defined as a reflection of how the institution uses financial and human resources and uses them efficiently and effectively in a way that makes it able to analyze its goals (Mahdi & Belkacem, 2017). Organizational performance is the output of value that the system produces in the form of goods and services, and it also expresses the efficiency and effectiveness achieved by the organization (Shane, 2017). Performance is in two forms which are financial performance and nonfinancial (Akyuz & Opusunju, 2019). Performance is a general structure that refers to the operations of the enterprise (Opusunju et al, 2019). Opusunju et al (2017) noted that performance is a reflection of the productivity of members of an enterprise measured in terms of revenue, profit, growth, development, and expansion of the organization. Performance is defined as how an enterprise is doing in terms of an increase in profit, market share, product quality, and expansion about other enterprises in the same industry (Akyuz & Opusunju, 2019). Performance is measured using diverse parameters by different organizations some firms measure it through expansion, survival, the number of employees, and capital employed (Akyuz & Opusunju, 2020). The indicators of performance are revenue, return on investment, profitability and market share.

Hence, whenever the key performance indicators are in favorable states, it indicates efficiency (Lyndon & Timi, 2019). For this study, firms' performance will be measured using a balanced scorecard that includes four dimensions: competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and profitability (Wilden & Gudergan, 2017).

2.2 Theoretical Framework Goal Setting Theory

Goal-setting theory was developed inductively within industrial/organizational (I/O) psychology over a 25-year period, based on some 400 laboratory and field studies. These studies showed that specific, high (hard) goals lead to a higher level of task performance than do easy goals or vague, abstract goals such as the exhortation to "do one's best." So long as a person is committed to the goal, has the requested ability to attain it, and does not have conflicting goals, there is a positive, linear relationship between goal difficulty and task performance. Because goals refer to future valued outcomes, the setting of goals is first and foremost a discrepancy creating process. It implies discontent with one's present condition and the desire to attain an object or outcome. Goals are related to affect in that goals set the primary standard for self-satisfaction with performance. High, or hard, goals are motivating because they require one to attain more in order to be satisfied than do low, or easy, goals. Feelings of success in the workplace occur to the extent that people see that they are able to grow and meet job challenges by pursuing and attaining goals that are important and meaningful (Latham, 2006). Goal setting strategies is a process of coming up with the direction of attention and effort towards task-relevant behaviors and actions. The authors define goal setting as "a formal program of setting numerical or quantitative performance goals for individuals" and that "all formal goal setting programs share the common objectives of increasing employee motivation and performance." The importance of goal is aptly defined by as representing "a way of keeping score" and that "by helping employees define their personal goals, managers are putting them on the path towards achieving the organization goals." (Lunenburg, 2011).

2.3 Empirical Studies

Bonn, Caren and Zachary (2018) examine the effect of mission and vision on organizational performance in private universities in Kenya. The specific research question is how do mission and vision affect organization performance in private universities in Kenya? This was a correlational study which adopted a positivist philosophy. The study population comprised of all 17 private universities in Kenya accredited by Commission of University

Education. The unit of analysis was the board of directors, vice chancellors, heads of departments (finance, sports, human resource, research, quality assurance) and academic deans (business school) which was 136. A census technique was used in the study with frequency distributions, percentages and means for descriptive statistical analysis while correlations and regression analyses were used for inferential statistics. The study found that, mission and vision explained a significant proportion of variance in organizational performance, $R^2 = .633$. The significance value in testing the reliability of the model for the relationship between Mission and Vision on

organizational performance was $F(1, 122) = 208.929, p = 0.00$. Therefore, the model was found to be statistically significant in predicting the relationship between the study variables. The study found that for every unit change in mission and vision, organizational performance increases by 0.867 hence implying a positive impact of mission and vision on organizational performance. Based on the findings, the study concluded that there was a significant relationship between all the independent variables and organizational performance the dependent variable.

Oluwaseyi, Onu and Akinlabi (2021) investigated the effect of mission statement on profitability of selected deposit money banks in Lagos State, Nigeria. Survey research design was adopted, 484 staff of 5 banks in Lagos State were sampled and data collated. Linear regression analysis was adopted and the result shows that Mission Statement had positive significant effect on profitability ($\beta = 0.446, t = 11.019, R^2 = 0.215, p < 0.05$). It was concluded that Mission Statement affects the profitability of selected deposit money banks. Sajjad, Sajjad and Mohammad (2020) identified the relationship between the mission statement components and the performance components. Moreover, it tries to help managers to state the high quality of the mission statement in their firms. The six-component mission statement was developed to measure the completeness the of firm's mission statement, and the BSC wd so as to measure the firms' performance. The BSC includes four dimensions: financial, customer, internal process and learning and growth. In this research, field research technique was applied, and questionnaires were used in order to gather data. The statistical population was 35 firms. Totally, 1400 questionnaires were passed out, 40 questionnaires in each firm, out of which 1230 questionnaires were returned. SPSS 18 was utilized to analyze the data. Results indicated a significant positive relationship between the components of the mission statement and some of the performance components. The most significant positive relationship was found between the purpose and the financial component, and the least significant positive relationship was found between the vision and the internal presses. In addition, the financial dimension was related to all the mission components. As a result, improving the biscmxi firm's mission statement will improve financial performance.

3.1 Methodology

A descriptive survey design was used in this study. The population comprises the Organization of Women in International Trade (OWIT) members which is leading actor in the non-oil export business in Nigeria. The OWIT has a total of one thousand five hundred members in Nigeria which form the population of this study. Sample size determination was used to have a sizeable number of respondents participating in the study. To this end, Gill, Johnson and Clark (2010), as cited in Teherdoost's (2017) sample size determination table, was adopted at 0.05 margin error and a confidence level of 95. Based on the sample size table, the sample population is now three hundred and six (306) respondents as depicted in Table 1:

Table 1: Determination of Sample Size for a Given Population

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The variance of the Population.

P=50%

Confidence Level =95%

Margin of Error

Population Size	0.05	0.03	0.01
50	44	48	50
75	63	70	74
100	79	91	99
150	108	132	148
200	132	168	196
250	151	203	244
300	168	234	291
400	196	291	384
500	217	340	475
600	234	384	565
700	248	423	652
800	260	457	738
1000	278	516	906
1500	306	624	1297
2000	322	696	1655
3000	341	787	2286
5000	357	879	3288
10000	370	964	4899
25000	378	1023	6939
50000	381	1045	8037
100000	383	1056	8762
250000	384	1063	9249
500000	384	1065	9423
1000000	384	1066	9513
10000000	384	1070	9545

Source: Gill, Johnson and Clark, 2010 cited in Teherdoost (2017)

The study used convenient sampling method and convenience sampling was also adopted in selecting respondents that participated in the study. This method was used because meeting all the members in the middle, and senior management level of the selected organisation is unlikely. In addition, availability and willingness were considered.

A structured questionnaire was administered and collects from the respondent from the Organisation of Women in International Trade (OWIT) members. The questionnaire was designed using Five Likert scales ranging from strongly agree - strongly disagree was adopted for this study. For data analysis, the study used descriptive and inferential analysis methods. The Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) is used to model the regression analysis that is used to test the hypotheses to determine if there is an effect relationship between each of the independent variables and the dependent variable. The PLS path modelling method was developed by World (1982). The PLS algorithm is a sequence of regressions in terms of weight vectors. The weight vectors that will be obtained at convergence shall satisfy fixed point equations. PLS-SEM is a non-parametric method that does not require that the data meet certain distributional assumptions. However, the parametric significant tests (e.g. as used in regression analyses) cannot be applied to test whether coefficients such as outer weights, outer loadings and path coefficients are significant. Instead, PLS-SEM relies on a non-parametric bootstrap procedure (Davison & Hinkley, 1997; Efron & Tibshirani, 1986) to test the significance of various results such path coefficients, Cronbach's alpha, HTMT, and R^2 values and Q^2 . Evaluating PLS-SEM results involves examining the measurement models, which differs for reflective and formative constructs. If the measurement models meet required criteria, researchers then need to assess the structural model (Hair, *et al.*, 2016). The first step in reflective measurement model assessment involves examining the indicator loadings. Loadings above 0.708 are recommended, since they indicate that the construct explains more than 50 percent of the indicator's variance, thus providing acceptable item reliability.

The second step is assessing internal consistency reliability, most often using Joreskog's (1971) composite reliability. Higher values generally indicate higher levels of reliability.

For example, reliability values between 0.60 and 0.70 are considered "acceptable in exploratory research", values between 0.70 and 0.90 range from "satisfactory to good". But values of 0.95 and higher are problematic, since they indicate that the items are redundant, thereby reducing construct validity (Diamantopoulos, *et al.*, 2012; Drolet & Morrison, 2001). Cronbach's alpha is another measure of internal consistency reliability that assumes similar thresholds but produces lower values than composite reliability.

The third step is to assess the convergent validity of each construct measure. Convergent validity is the extent to which the construct converges in order to explain the variance of its items. The metric used for evaluating a construct's convergent validity, is the average variance extracted (AVE) for all items on each construct. To calculate the AVE, one must square the loading of each indicator on a construct and compute the mean value. The minimum acceptable AVE is 0.50 or higher—an AVE of 0.50 or higher indicates that the construct explains 50 percent or more of the variance of the items that make up the construct.

The fourth step is to assess discriminant validity, which is the extent to which a construct is empirically distinct from other constructs in the structural model. Fornell and Larcker (1981) proposed the traditional metric and suggested that each construct's AVE should be compared to the squared inter-construct correlation (as a measure of shared variance) of that same construct and all other reflectively measured constructs in the structural model—the shared variance for all model constructs should not be larger than their AVEs. Recent research indicates, however, that this metric is not suitable for discriminant validity assessment. For example, Henseler, *et al.*, (2014) showed that the Fornell-Larcker criterion does not perform well, particularly when the indicator loadings on a construct differ only slightly (e.g., all the indicator loadings are between 0.65 and 0.85). As a replacement, Henseler, *et al.*, (2014) proposed the heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) of the correlations (also see Voorhees, *et al.*, 2005). The HTMT ratio is defined as the mean value of the item correlations across constructs (i.e. the heterotrait-hetero method correlations) relative to the (geometric) mean of the average correlations for the items measuring the same construct (i.e., the monotrait-hetero method correlations). Discriminant validity problems are present when HTMT values are high.

Formative measurement models are evaluated based on (1) convergent validity, (2) indicator collinearity, and (3) statistical significance and relevance of the indicator weights (Hair, *et al.*, 2016). For formatively measured constructs, convergent validity is assessed by the correlation of the construct with an alternative measure of the same concept. Hair, *et al.*, (2016) suggested that the correlation of the formatively measured construct with the single item construct, measuring the same concept, should be 0.70 or higher.

The variance inflation factor (VIF) is often used to evaluate collinearity of the formative indicators. When VIF values are high, the level of collinearity is greater. VIF values of 5 or above indicate collinearity issues among the predictor constructs. However, collinearity issues can also occur at lower VIF values of 3 (Becker, *et al.*, 2013; Mason & Perreault 1991). Ideally, the VIF values should be close to 3 and lower. Researchers need to assess the indicator weights' statistical significance and relevance (i.e. size). Since the PLS-SEM is a non-parametric method, bootstrapping is used to determine statistical significance (Chin, 1998). Hair, *et al.*, (2016) suggested using BCa bootstrap confidence intervals for significance testing in case the bootstrap distribution of

the indicator weights is skewed. Otherwise, researchers should use the percentile method to construct bootstrap-based confidence intervals (Aguirre-Urreta & Ronkko, 2018).

When measurement model assessment is satisfactory, the next step in evaluating PLS-SEM results is assessing the structural model. Standard assessment criteria, which should be considered, include the coefficient of determination (R^2), the blindfolding-based cross validated redundancy measure Q^2 , as well as the statistical significance and relevance of the path coefficients. In addition, researchers should assess their model's out-of-sample predictive power by using the PLS predict procedure (Shmueli, *et al.*, 2016), assuming the sample size is large enough. Structural model coefficients for the relationships between the constructs are derived from estimating a series of regression equations. Before assessing the structural relationships, collinearity must be examined to make sure it does not bias the regression results.

If collinearity is not an issue, the next step is examining the R^2 value of the endogenous construct(s). The R^2 measure the variance, which is explained in each of the endogenous constructs, and is therefore a measure of the model's explanatory power (Shmueli & Koppius, 2011). The R^2 is also referred to as in-sample predictive power (Rigdon, 2012). The R^2 ranges from 0 to 1, with higher values indicating a greater explanatory power. As a guideline, the R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 can be considered substantial, moderate and weak (Hair, *et al.*, 2011; Henseler, *et al.*, 2009).

The Structural Equation Model that is adopted for this study is as follows:

The model depicts the effect of measurement variables of mission statement on performance.

4.1 Results

Table 2: Firm's Mission Statement

S/N	Firms Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
FMS1	The mission statement is periodically reviewed and updated to reflect environmental changes.	41 (15.1) (7.7) (37.5)	41 (24.6)	21 (7.7)	102 (32.4)	67 (23.5)
FMS2	My organisation has sufficient resources to carry out its mission.	32 (11.8)	73 (26.8)	15 (5.5)	88 (32.4)	64 (23.5)
FMS3	The organisation's writing mission statement reflects its purpose, values, and target customers.	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	12 (4.4)	129 (47.4)	131 (48.2)
FMS4	My organisation has a welldefined mission statement.	4 (1.5)	7 (2.6)	16 (5.9)	105 (38.6)	104 (51.5)
FMS5	My organisation usually updates its mission statement when necessary.	24 (8.8)	69 (25.4)	32 (11.8)	100 (36.8)	47 (17.3)

Table 2 shows the respondents perceived usefulness. This was measured with five (5) items, as indicated in Table 4.3. One of the items for measuring a firm's mission statement was to find out if the mission statement is periodically reviewed and updated to reflect environmental changes. It was discovered that 169(62.0%) of the respondents strongly agreed and agreed, 21(7.7%) of the respondents neither agreed nor disagree, while 82(30.2%) of the respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. However, most of the respondents agree that the mission statement is periodically reviewed and updated to reflect environmental changes. It was also in the researcher's interest to know if the organisation has sufficient resources to carry out its mission. 152(55.9%) positively affirmed the statement, 15(5.5%) neither agreed nor disagreed with the statement, while 105 (38.6%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement. This reveals that respondents believe that organisation has sufficient resources to carry out its mission. The researcher also wanted to find out if the organisation has a mission statement in writing that reflects its purpose, values, and target customers; 260(95.6%) are of the opinion or belief that the organisation has a mission statement in writing that reflects its purpose, values, and target customers 12(4.4%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement. This implies that the organisation has a mission statement in writing that reflects its purpose, values, and target customers. Also, it

was discovered from the descriptive statistics that 209(90.1%) strongly agreed and agreed that the organisation has a well-defined mission statement, 16(5.9%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement, while 11(4.1%) had a contrary opinion.

Table 3 Firm's Competitiveness

S/N	Firm's Competitiveness	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean	SD
FC1	exploit all market opportunities that have been presented to the organisation	5 (1.8)	46 (16.9)	28 (10.3)	147 (54.0)	46 (16.9)	3.67	1.01
FC 2	cope with all competitive threats from rival firms.	5 (1.8)	25 (9.2)	38 (14.0)	145 (53.3)	59 (21.7)	3.85	0.93
FC 3	put a strong emphasis on promotions and effective advertisement.	5 (1.8)	15 (5.5)	22 (8.1)	151 (55.5)	79 (29.0)	4.04	0.87
FC 4	develop a strong desire to be more successful than competitors.	10 (3.7)	10 (3.7)	21 (7.7)	138 (50.7)	93 (34.2)	4.02	0.96
FC 5	constantly coordinates its level of activities to meet customer needs.	10 (3.7)	10 (3.7)	21 (7.7)	138 (50.7)	93 (34.2)	4.08	0.95

Average 3.93 0.94 Table 3 show that the

Firm's Competitiveness was measured using five (5) items. One of such items for the measurement of a Firm's Competitiveness was to find out if, over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to: exploit all market opportunities that have been presented to the organisation and 193(70.9%) of them agreed and strongly agreed. On the other hand, 51(18.7%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with the statement, while 28(10.3%) of the respondents were not sure what to believe, with a mean score of 3.67 and standard deviation of 1.01. This suggests that over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to: exploit all market opportunities that have been presented to the organisation. The researcher went further to know if, over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to cope with all competitive threats from rival firms, and 204(75.0%) of the respondent agreed and strongly agreed with this statement, 30(11.0%) strongly disagreed and disagreed, while 38(14.0%) neither agreed nor disagreed to this statement, with a mean score of 3.85 and a standard deviation of 0.93. this further explains that over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to: cope with all competitive threats from rival firms. Also, 230(84.5%) respondents agreed and strongly agreed that over the last three years, the organization's competitive strategy has helped to put a strong emphasis on promotions and effective advertisement. Conversely, 20(7.3%) of the respondent negated the statement, while 22(8.1%) were not sure what to believe, with a mean

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score of 4.04 and standard deviation of 0.87. This reveals that over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to: put a strong emphasis on promotions and effective advertisement.

Moreover, the item used was to find out if, over the last three years, the organization's competitive strategy has helped to: develop a strong desire to be more successful than the competitors. 231(84.9%) of the respondents agreed and strongly agreed with this statement, 21(7.7%) neither agreed nor disagreed, while 20(7.4%) disagreed and strongly disagreed with this statement with a mean score of 4.02 and a standard deviation of 0.96. This suggests that over the last three years, the competitive strategy of the organisation has helped to: develop a strong desire to be more successful than the competitors

Furthermore, the item used for this measurement was to determine if, over the last three years, the organization's competitive strategy has helped to constantly coordinate its level of activities to meet customer needs. 231(84.9%) respondents strongly affirm this notion, 21(7.7%) feel indifferent about the notion, whereas 20(7.4%) refute this claim with a mean score of 4.08 and standard deviation of 0.94. This shows that over the last three years, the organization's competitive strategy has helped to constantly coordinate its level of activities to meet customer need

Table 4 Market Share

			U	A	SA	Mean	SD
MS1	Over the last five years, the percentage of total purchases of this company's product has been considerable.	0 10	48 (17.9)	161 (59.2)	53 (19.5)	3.95	0.72
MS 2	Over the last five years, a portion of this company within the entire market in which it operates has been substantial.	0 sales25	60 (22.1)	154 (56.6)	33 (12.1)	3.72	0.80
MS 3	Our organizations percentage of the Market Share	0 24	50 (18.4)	153 (56.3)	45 (16.5)	3.81	0.82
S/N	SD industry's total income is significant.		(0.0)	(8.8)	(18.4)	(56.3)	(16.5)
MS 4	My company looks out for business diversification opportunities to stabilize its market share.	0 5	19 (7.0)	138 (50.7)	110 (40.0)	4.30	0.68
Average						3.95	0.76

Table 4 reveal that in order to determine if respondents' market share, the combination of strongly agreed and agreed as expressed by the respondents shows that 214(78.7%) of the respondents were of the opinion that Over the last five years, the percentage of total purchases of this company's product has been considerable, 48(17.9%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement while 10(3.7%) of the respondents had an opposing view with a mean score of 3.95 and a standard deviation of 0.72. this show that most of the which accounted for 78% are positive that Over the last five years, the percentage of total purchases of this company's product has been considerable.

In addition, it was in the researcher's interest to find out if, over the last five years, a portion of sales of this company within the entire market in which it operates has been substantial. the combination of strongly agreed and agreed as expressed by the respondents shows that 187(68.7%) of the respondents believed and belief that Over the last five years, a portion of sales of this company within the entire market in which it operates has been substantial., 60(22.1%) of the respondents were indifferent to the statement, while 25(9.2%) of the respondents had contrary with a mean score of 3.72 and a standard deviation of 0.20. this show that most of the respondents believe that over the last five years, a portion of sales of this company within the entire market in which it operates has been substantial. Also,

198(72.8%) respondents agreed and strongly agreed organisation's percentage of the industry's total income is significant. Conversely, 24(8.8%) disagreed and strongly disagreed, while 50(18.4%) were not sure what to believe, with a mean score of 3.18 and a standard deviation of 0.82. This reveals that the organisation's percentage of the industry's total income is significant.

In order to determine if a company looks out for business diversification opportunities to stabilise its market share. The combination of strongly agree and agreed shows that 248(90.7%) are of the opinion or belief that the company looks out for business diversification opportunities to stabilise its market share, 19(7.0%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement, while 5(1.8%) of the respondent have contrary believe that the statement with a mean score of 4.30 and standard deviation of 0.68. this reveals that most of the population is of the opinion that the company looks out for business diversification opportunities to stabilise its market share.

Table 5 Service Quality

S/N	Service Quality	SD	D	U	A	SA	Mean	SD
SQ1	Our organisation provides prompt services to the customers.	0 (0.0)	10 (3.7)	17 (6.3)	150 (55.1)	95 (34.9)	4.21	0.72
SQ 2	Our organisation has customers' best interests at heart.	9 (3.3)	5 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	108 (39.7)	150 (55.1)	4.41	0.87
SQ 3	Our organisation provides services at the time required.	5 (1.8)	22 (8.1)	12 (4.4)	128 (47.1)	105 (38.6)	4.13	0.95
SQ4	Our organisation gives individual attention to customers.	5 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	24 (8.8)	138 (50.7)	105 (38.6)	4.24	0.76
SQ5	Our organisation is always willing to provide service to customers.	5 (1.8)	5 (1.8)	0 (0.0)	133 (48.2)	133 (48.2)	4.39	0.76
Average							4.28	0.81

Table 5 how to determine if respondents had Service Quality, the combination of strongly agreed and agreed as expressed by the respondents shows that 245(90.0%) of the respondents were of the opinion that organisation provides prompt services to the customers, 17(6.3%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement while 10(3.7%) of the respondents had an opposing view with a mean score of 4.21 and stand deviation of 0.72.

It was in the interest of the researcher to find out if the organisation has customers' best interests at heart. The combination of strongly agreed and agreed as expressed by the respondents shows that 258(94.9%) of the respondents were of the opinion that the organisation has customers' best interests at heart, 0(0.0%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement while 14(5.1%) of the respondents had a contrary view with a mean score of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 0.87. This implies that most of the respondents believe that organisation has customers' best interests at heart. Also, to find out if the organisation provides services at the time required, 233(85.7%) of the respondents were of the opinion that the organisation provides services at the time required, and 12(4.4%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement while 27(9.9%) of the respondents had an opposing view about the statement with the mean score of 4.13 and standard deviation of 0.95.

In order to find out if an organisation gives individual attention to their customers. The combination of strongly agreed and agreed as expressed by the respondents, it was observed that 243(89.3%) of the respondents were of the opinion that organisation gives individual attention to the customers, 24(8.8%) of the respondents were indifferent about the statement while 5(1.8%) of the respondents had an opposing view about the statement with a mean score of 4.24 and standard deviation of 0.76. this show that the majority of the respondents believe that organisation gives individual attention to the customers. In order to determine if the organisation is always willing to provide prompt service to customers, the combination of strongly agree and agreed shows that 266(96.4%) are of the opinion that the organisation is always willing to provide prompt service to customers, 0(0.00%) neither agree nor disagree with the statement while 10(3.6%) of the respondent have contrary believe that the statement with a mean score of 4.39 and standard deviation of 0.76.

Fig. 1: Test of Hypotheses

Figure 1 shows the PLS algorithm model of the firm's mission statement development and firm's performance with the loading values of each item of measurement of the constructs.

Figure 1 describes the PLS Bootstrapping Model with β and P-coefficient of the value of the firm's mission statement development and firm's performance (competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, service quality). At a p-value of 0.05, all the values of the firm's mission statement development, competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality measurements obtained in the research instrument are significant.

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	Loading		P- value		Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha
		VIF		AVE		
Constructs	≥ 0.7	< 3.0	$< .05$	≥ 0.5	≥ 0.8	> 0.7
Firm's Mission Statement (FMS)				0.760	0.926	0.893
FMS1	0.853	2.200	0.000			
FMS2	0.797	1.632	0.000			
FMS3	0.893	2.001	0.000			
FMS4	0.937	1.521	0.000			
Firm's Competitiveness (FC)				0.656	0.884	0.827
FC1	0.747	1.587	0.000			
FC2	0.808	1.254	0.000			
FC3	0.868	1.369	0.000			
FC4	0.803	1.854	0.000			
Market Share (MS)				0.672	0.891	0.835
MS1	0.877	1.773	0.000			
MS2	0.707	2.222	0.000			
MS3	0.811	1.965	0.000			
MS4	0.872	2.113	0.000			
Perceived Customer Satisfaction (PCS)				0.616	0.865	0.799
PCS1	0.709	1.421	0.000			
PCS2	0.816	1.900	0.000			
PCS3	0.799	2.556	0.000			
PCS4	0.809	1.512	0.000			
Service Quality				0.638	0.898	0.859
SQ1	0.789	1.700	0.000			
SQ2	0.817	1.652	0.000			
SQ3	0.802	1.741	0.000			

SQ4	0.726	1.520	0.000
SQ5	0.854	1.963	0.000

Table 5: Construct validity and Reliability

Table 5 shows the factor loadings of all the measurement items for the firm's mission statement development and the firm's performance (competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, service quality). The validity and reliability of the instrument were also assessed using composite reliability, average variance extracted (AVE) computation and Cronbach Alpha. Meanwhile, the recommended requirements for factor loading, composite reliability, AVE, and Cronbach Alpha were met. However, convergent and discriminant validity were also considered for determining construct validity in the study. Convergent validity is evidence of an association between a firm's mission statement development and a firm's performance. Also, to test for common method bias, the variance inflation factor (IVF) was used (CMB). While a VIF value of one indicates that collinearity is completely absent, most researchers recommend a VIF value of ten as the cutoff. Other researchers advocated a more conservative cutoff of 2.5 to 5 points (James et al., 2017; Kock, 2015). As shown in Table 4.11, all the VIF values for each item in each variable measurement are well below the conservative threshold of 5.

Table 7 Heterotrait-monotrait discriminant

	FMS	FC	MC	PCS	QS
FMS					
FC	0.442				
MC	0.412	0.774			
PCS	0.694	0.683	0.751		

The correlations' heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio was used to assess discriminant validity. The upper confidence intervals are all lower than one, and all of the HTMT values were found to be significantly different from one. Furthermore, the analysis results show that all of the values are less than the critical value of HTMT 0.85. Furthermore, the average heterotraithetero method correlation is less than the average monotrait-heteromethod correlation. The discriminant validity is thus established. Table 7 depicts the heterotrait-monotrait discriminant value. Table 8 Model Fit for the Variable

Model	Estimated
SRMR	0.076
d_ ULS	2.137
d_ G	0.991
Chi-Square	492.050
NFI	0.953

As displayed in Table 8, All the model fit indices were found to be satisfactory. The standardised residual average between the observed matrix and the hypothesised covariance matrices is represented by SRMR (Chen, 2007). The SRMR is a model fit estimation metric. When the SRMR is less than 0.08, it is considered reliable. This study model's SRMR was also 0.076, indicating a good fit for this research. With a chi-square value of 492.050, the NFI estimate for this study is 0.953, which is higher than the benchmark of 0.90. Also, to determine the PLS-SEM predictive relevance of the constructs of measurement and the data points of indicators, the Q^2 values were used. The Q^2 values for FC, MS, PCS, and SQ are 0.169, 0.176, 0.206 and 0.146, which is larger than zero. This suggests that the PLS path model has predictive relevance for the constructs. In the same vein, the F square was used to determine the effect size. The f-square values for FC, MS, PCS, and SQ are 0.180, 0.184, 0.630 and 0.353, as indicated in Table 4.14. This implies that the sample effect is considered large.

Table 9 Coefficient value of Variables

Variables	Path Co-efficient	SE	T-Statistics	P Values	R ²	F ²	Q ²	Decision
H ₀₁ FMS → FC	0.390	0.085	4.567	0.000	0.152	0.180	0.069	Significant
H ₀₁ FMS → MS	0.359	0.109	3.292	0.000	0.129	0.184	0.076	Significant
H ₀₁ FMS → PCS	0.622	0.059	10.623	0.000	0.386	0.630	0.206	Significant
H ₀₁ FMS → QS	0.511	0.076	6.706	0.000	0.261	0.353	0.146	Significant

Table 9 depicts the smart partial least squared statistical results, which focused on the relationship between a firm's mission statement development and firm's performance (firm's competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, service quality). The findings show that a firm's mission statement development significantly affects competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality.

The findings revealed that firm's mission statement development has significant influence on firm's competitiveness at ($\beta= 0.390$, $R^2=0.152$, $t\text{-statistics}=4.567>1.96$, $P\text{-value} =0.000 <0.05$). The Path coefficient of 0.390 implies a fair degree of relationship between a firm's mission statement development and a firm's competitiveness. The R^2 value of 0.152 indicates that a 15.2% variance in firm's competitiveness can be explained by firm's mission statement development.

The findings revealed that firm's mission statement development has significant influence on market share at ($\beta= 0.359$, $R^2=0.129$, $t\text{-statistics}=3.292>1.96$, $P\text{-value} =0.000 <0.05$). The Path coefficient of 0.359 implies a fair degree of relationship between a firm's mission statement development and market share. The R^2 value of 0.129 indicates that a 12.9% variance in market share can be explained by firm's mission statement development. The findings revealed that firm's mission statement development has significant influence on perceived customer satisfaction at ($\beta= 0.622$, $R^2=0.386$, $t\text{-statistics}=10.623>1.96$, $P\text{-value} =0.000 <0.05$). The Path coefficient of 0.622 implies a considerable degree of relationship between a firm's mission statement development and perceived customer satisfaction. The R^2 value of 0.386 indicates that a 38.6% variance in perceived customer satisfaction can be explained by the firm's mission statement development.

The findings revealed that firm's mission statement development has significant influence on service quality at ($\beta= 0.511$, $R^2=0.261$, $t\text{-statistics}=6.706>1.96$, $P\text{-value} =0.000 <0.05$). The Path coefficient of 0.511 implies a moderate degree of relationship between a firm's mission statement development and service quality. The R^2 value of 0.261 indicates that a 26.1% variance in service quality can be explained by firm's mission statement development. According to the statistical analysis presented in Table 4.14, perceived customer satisfaction has the highest predictive value, followed by service quality, firm competitiveness, and market share.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The study found that a firm's mission statement development significantly affects competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality in non-oil export with a particular reference to women's organization in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria. This implies that mission statement development contributes significantly to the performance in terms of competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality in non-oil export with a particular reference to women organizations in international trade in Abuja- Nigeria. The study is in line with the finding of Bonn, Caren, and Zachary (2018) who found a significant effect of the mission statement on performance. The study is also in line with goal setting theory.

5.1 Conclusion and Recommendation

The study concluded that the mission statement will foster perceived customer satisfaction if it is periodically reviewed and updated to reflect changes in the environment. Furthermore, if there are sufficient resources to carry out the mission in a way that reflects its purpose, values, and target customers, then it will foster customer satisfaction. In especially when the company is dedicated to satisfying the expectations of customers, is more customer-focused, and routinely reviews the demands of customers by closely collaborating with them in the exploration and development of new ideas. Not only that, but moreover, the service quality, competitiveness, and market share of a company could all benefit from having a well-defined mission statement. This will be achievable if the company delivers prompt services to the customers, has the best interests of the customers at heart, provides the services at the time required, gives particular attention to the customers, and is always eager to provide prompt services to customers. This has the potential to boost sales, ensure consistent income, and ultimately improve the organization's bottom line. Furthermore, the organization will be able to make the most of all market opportunities and build strategies for dealing with the challenges posed by competing businesses in the context of satisfying the requirements of customers.

The study recommended that mission statement development in terms of periodic reviews and updates of the mission statement that reflect environmental changes, purpose, values, and target customers, as well as sufficient resources to carry out the mission. All of these contribute significantly to a firm's competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, and service quality. Efforts should be made by the leadership of the Organization of Women in International Trade to regularly update their mission statement that reflects environmental changes, purpose, values, and target customers, allocate adequate resources to carry out the mission statement to foster the firm's competitiveness, perceived customer satisfaction, market share, service quality.

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